

Stress Management –Impact among Employees

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Abstract:

Stress is a universal phenomenon that manifests itself in people mainly as a result of pressure caused by experiences or difficult situations. Delay in completion of work, weakening of organizational and planning efficiency, increase in error rate when performing manipulative and cognitive tasks, depression and feelings of helplessness and hypersensitivity are the greatest effects of stress on the productivity of specialists. Based on the results, it was concluded that stress has a significant impact on professionals and thus affects the level of productivity . Therefore, professionals were advised to show self-control and good self-esteem; engage in continuous professional development to better organize skills, integrate work within specific project boundaries, and delegate, delegate, and break work into manageable parts to help you manage stress. The study tried to find out the causes of stress among employees and the means by which employees cope with stress in workplaces. The second part of the article explains some stress management strategies, how to get social support, using stress management programs , reducing workplace stress by improving the work environment and work organization.

Keywords: Industries, Workplace, Factors, Stress, Stress Management

Introduction

More and more employees experience stress at work. They can adapt to more than workloads, long hours or rapid changes in innovation, deadlines to meet changing needs. The nature of business has now changed and the possibility of permanent employment has been replaced by an emphasis on implementation. Stress is now seen as a legitimate well-being and occupational safety issue. Stress can cause a variety of terrible and disabling feelings and symptoms, such as brain pain, back pain, upset stomach, nervousness and lethargy. It therefore leads to lack of profit, wear and tear and long term illness if not avoided. So pressure control has become important for every connection. Stress Management is increasingly in the spotlight today, especially in the private sector. It is not a peaceful activity. Everyone in their work is under pressure and stress when they exceed the responsibilities delegated to them. The study shows that a large number of employees are subjected to high pressure due to their work, and the explanations for this pressure are long working hours, inappropriate remuneration frameworks, labor strife, lack of independence in working life, authoritarian culture, leaders supported by representatives. Workers may experience various side effects that indicate significant level pressure among them. Be that as it may, if these side effects are not really noticed in the beginning, they can cause real health problems for workers such as sadness, heart problems, diabetes etc. More and more employers are turning to stress management to solve these problems. Stress management can help people improve their response to stress and reduce environmental stressors. This not only helps reduce stress at the individual level, but also at the organizational level.

STRESS: Stress is the "wear and tear" on our mind and body as we try to adapt to a constantly changing state. Stress is generally characterized as: "A multifaceted response to circumstances that are perceived to attempt or, on the other hand, threaten the well-being of a person." Stress is also a physiological and psychological condition that prepares a person to adapt to an unfriendly or uncompromising environment.

- According to Richard S. Lazarus, "Stress as a condition or feeling experienced when a person perceives that demands exceed the personal and social resources the individual is able to mobilize."
- According to Hans Selye, "Stress is the body's nonspecific response to a demand placed on it."

Causes of Stress

Work-related factors: job boredom, dangerous and undesirable working conditions, lack of secrecy, work frustration, lack of union, etc.

Extra Authoritative: Elements such as in today's intelligent world of modern technology, stress expanded, expanded, mechanical changes, social obligations and rapid social changes are other variables that cause additional pressure.

Individual: Elements such as different desires that employees relatives, partners, bosses and subordinates have the inability to see them in values, pressure on others pressure causing personal components are different character traits such as anxiety, feeling under time pressure, strength, inflexibility, etc. Family problems, individual financial problems, unexpected career changes also cause stress.

Organization: Elements such as pay structure differentiation, strict rules and guidelines, peer pressure, conflicting goals/uncertainty of goals, ineffective communication, less open career opportunities, lack of employee investment in key management, excessive managerial control over employees, etc.

Stress management: Stress management is the need of the hour. No matter how hard we try to overcome a stressful situation, life seems to find better ways to worry us and tease us with anxiety attacks. Stress management isolates sources of stress early in life and keeps distance from them.

Importance of stress management: The goal of stress management is to create a situation that is beneficial to the party, employees and managers.

A) Employee benefits:

- Reduces stress
- Less absenteeism due to stress-related disorders
- Less unpleasant, increasingly experienced work environment
- Help with child/elderly care plans
- Better mood
- Less negative pressure
- Better relationship both at work and outside

B) Organizational benefits:

- Employee satisfaction
- Measurable increase in responsibility
- Better collaboration and correspondence
- Attract/retain employees
- Reduce labour turnover
- Increase employee efficiency
- Better reputation or goodwill

Objectives: Stress has been widely studied over the past hundred years. The main objective of this research is the following

- 1) The effect of stress on a person's life.
- 2) The importance of stress management.
- 3) To what extent stress management techniques are successful in managing stress.
- 4.) Know different methods and techniques to reduce stress.

Research Methodology: The study is based on secondary sources in the form of research articles and websites. Based on this secondary information, this article discussed the stress management of employees in various industries. Some introspection was also mentioned in relation to stress management.

Findings: Most workers fear that a lack of quality work will bring them down. Expectations for everyday convenience, linked to the growing horizon of new application possibilities, increased profitability and the nature of work, time constraints and strained labor relations, increase the pressure on the workforce. Human relations, authority, emotional factors, job assignment, overtime commitment, extended work. The feeling of anxiety among employees is different according to work and, at best, according to responsibilities, and in addition, individual pressure tolerance is unique to its groups. Stress and performance, on the contrary, correspond to each other.

Conclusion: From this we can conclude that in the current situation, every child going to school or an employee has stress in different places. Too much pressure is not good for well-being. Management must create a healthy work environment, and it is also important to prepare at all levels to limit stress and promote success and profitability. The entire management can implement various fun but motivating activities in the organization. Instead of an annual trip, it could be taken on a quarterly vacation. More psychological games should be introduced to find out the feelings of the employee so that necessary measures can be taken. A weekly meditation and yoga class could be another way to deal with stress, because the cause can be limitless, but the problem is the same.

References: • Ashford S.J. (1988). Individual Strategies for Coping with Stress during Organizational Transitions. *Journal of Applied Behavioural Science*.24, 19-36

• Beehr T. A. & Newman J. E. (1978). Job Stress, Employee Health and Organizational effectiveness: A facet analysis, model, and literature review. *Personnel Psychology* 31(4),665-699.

• Cooper C.L. & Payne, R. (1978). *Stress at Work*. Chichester: Djebarni R (1996) the impact of stress in site management effectiveness, construction management and economics 14, 281-293.

- Cooper CL, Marshall J. Occupational sources of stress: a review of the literature relating to coronary heart disease and mental ill health. *J Occup Health Psychol* 1976;49:11–28.
- Lazarus S, Folkman S. *Stress, appraisal and coping* . New York: Springer, 1984. A comprehensive account of the transactional model of stress and its management.
- Olpin M. & Hesson M (2007). *Stress Management for Life: A Research-Based Experiential Approach*. California: Wadsworth Publishing Company